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Oil Spill Cleanup for Automobile Pollution: The Performance of Raw and Treated Banana Stem Fiber

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Abstract

Automobile pollution occurs from the emissions of oil and grease from the vehicles that settled in the water. Oil spills are one of the problems that arise which is not only affecting human health but also has a greater impact on the environment. This paper focuses on the treatment method suitable in modified the natural fiber as a sorbent material for removing oil and grease from oil contaminated water. The sorbents that were used are from a natural source which is banana stem fiber. The efficiency of the sorbent was determined by measuring the concentration of oil before and after the adsorption process. The oil that uses is diesel. The sorbent will be compared with the untreated and the treated fiber. The alkaline solution of sodium Hydroxide (NaOH) and Potassium Hydroxide (KOH) have been selected. The use of alkaline solution can enhance the surface structure of the banana stem fiber. With the effect of the treatment, it can help the banana stem fiber to increase the percentage removal of oil.

Keywords: Automobile pollution, Banana Stem Fiber, Oil removal

INTRODUCTION

In this modernized era, vehicle usage being seen increasing from time to time due to the industrial revolution. There are many environmental problems occur which comes from vehicle activities such as automobile pollution. This pollution is the contaminants come from automobiles such as cars, trucks, vessel and any vehicle that burn gas. In line with the increasing of vehicle usage, an oil spill from vehicles had captured much attention due to its impact on the environment and other living things. These contaminants settled in the water and thus create water pollution.

Oil contamination in water bodies has been recognized as one of the major problems in water pollution. The existence of oil and grease comes from many sources such as vehicle activities, manufacturing processes, food production and much more. The impact of the oil spill has the possibility effect on aquatic livings and also drinking water resources. According to Sakari *et. al* (2010), the study states the pollution of the sources of petroleum is different based on the locations. Most of the oil spillage occurs because of the operational discharges from tanks.

Leaking oil from vessels goes to sea and ocean thus contaminate the water which causes toxicity to water-column and causes marine organisms to die which have direct contact include fish, invertebrates, and seaweed. Normally, oil spillage incidents happen during the operation of the fishing boat, small vessels and oil tanks and cargo cleaning. Immediate attention should be a focus on the environmental pollution that required actions from the petroleum industry, researchers, environmentalists and all stakeholders. In fact, oil operation histories also are not environment-friendly. Drilling, production, processing, transportation and seismic exploration of oil operations have an adverse impact on the environment. Furthermore, motor and lubricating oil used by automotive and industries also considered as one of the factors that may contribute to water pollution. Leaking oils from cars go to the street and further, washed from the street into the storm drain and our lakes, rivers, and streams.

The current technologies used in combating the spillage of oil are not economically friendly and sustainable. There is much requirement in minimizing the impact on the ecosystem and environment (Al-

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Majed, Adebayo & Hossain, 2012). Cleanup and recovery from oil contamination is difficult and involves many factors such as types of oil, the quantity of oil, the temperature of water and others. Oil can contaminate water bodies in two ways which are oil-in-water emulsion and water-in-oil emulsion (Hubbe *et al.*, 2013). Currently, there are many ways to remove the spills of oil and grease from water bodies which include physical, chemical and biological or bioremediation methods. Few examples of a current approach for containing oil spills are skimming, booms and burning the oil on the water surface (Sarbatly, Krishnaiah & Kamin, 2016). Al-Majed, Adebayo and Hossain (2012) also listed cleanup techniques such as by using mechanical tools, using chemical dispersants, steam flushing and also synthetic absorbents. Even though there are many ways to have been identified, but there are still exists some limitations where the treatment that uses for oily wastewater before disposal is still unsatisfactory. The reasons are because some of this technique is harmful either to humans and also the environment. For example, by using the burning methods, it can cause large quantities of smoke that can lead to an airborne problem. This statement is discussed by Al-Majed, Adebayo and Hossain (2012) when burning of oil at water bodies can produce dangerous substances such as carbon monoxide, sulfur dioxide and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs).

One of the most convenient ways to remove oil spills has been identified by using natural fiber. To contain the oil spill problem, one of the efficient and faster ways is by using the sorption method. Mostly, the sorbents that accessible are adsorbents and a small amount for absorbents. Classification of oil sorbents can be divided into three classes, which is inorganic mineral products, organic mineral product, and organic vegetable product (natural sorbents). Adsorption is known as the cheapest yet effective in term of removal of pollutants. According to a review by Wahi *et al.* (2013), adsorption is an attraction process between sorbent and sorbate in which sorbate will fill the outer layer of the sorbent.

In the adsorption process, the use of activated carbon as the adsorbent material is widely known as effective. However, there is a limitation in using activated carbon. One of the reasons is cost. The implementation of natural sorbent materials has been recognized in treating oil spills and grease from the water bodies due to their environmentally friendly characteristics. The use of natural materials as a sorbent is widely known in removing pollutants. Studies by Sun, Sun and Sun (2004), Teli and Valia (2012) and Sidik *et al.* (2012) show the use of natural materials in removing oil.

Agricultural waste such as banana, pineapple is commonly found in abundant in Malaysia. Banana plants are one of the common plants that can be found in Malaysia. After harvesting the branches, the remaining trunk will become a waste. According to a study by Mohapatra, Mishra and Sutar (2010), banana fibers can be used as a natural sorbent. However, there are a few problems that arise when using natural materials. The hydrophilicity of sorbent plays a major role in removing oil. The nature of natural materials is that the hydrophilicity characteristic is high thus removing oil will be lowered. The researcher tries to apply the modification to increase the hydrophobicity of the sorbent itself. One of the treatments is by using an alkaline treatment, where sorbent was soaked into an alkaline solution for a given period. The wax, lignin, pectin and natural oil that present on the surface of the material is removed when treated (Wahi *et al.*, 2013). It believes in increasing the enhancement of oil entrapment.

This paper highlights the uses of banana stem fiber as the natural sorbents to improve the removal of oil contaminants water. To enhance the sorption ability of banana stem fiber, Sodium Hydroxide (NaOH) and Potassium Hydroxide (KOH) was added to the untreated banana stem fiber. This empirical paper highlights the findings of banana stem fiber which has been chosen in determining the ability of oil absorption.

Crude oil is a natural resource found underground on land or sea which has different types over the world. Before being used, this crude oil needs to go through many processes which then refined into petroleum products. Diesel is one of the most valuable crude oil products as the energy sources to move the vehicle. It is widely used for the consumer around the world including land and sea transportation. Diesel has been chosen as it shows less volatile, low viscosity and excellent compositional uniformity. With this characteristic of oil, it can reduce transient change during experiments of chemical and physical characteristics (Abdullah, Rahmah & Man, 2010).

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

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The main focus of this study is to identify the adsorption treatment method that suitable for modified the natural fiber which is banana stem fiber in removing oil and grease in the water.

METHOD

Fig.1. shows the summary of banana stem fiber treatment. This treatment was divided into three stages which include the Preparation of Banana Stem Fiber, Treatment of the Banana Stem Fiber and preparation of oil contaminated water sample. Detail description of the stages is explained below.

Fig.1: Sample Preparation Of Banana Stem Fiber Treatment

A. Preparation of Banana Stems Fiber

Analytical reagent grade of sodium hydroxide (NaOH) and potassium hydroxide (KOH) was used in the experimental procedure. The banana fiber was prepared from the banana stem. The banana stem was taken from a banana farm in Selangor, Malaysia. To prepare banana fiber, the banana stem was processed to get the inner stem fiber. The banana stem was washed with tap water for two times and further washing by deionized water at least three times to remove dust and soluble impurities. The banana stem was then undergo rolling and tapping to remove its water content. The pressed rolled banana stem was then dried in an oven at 115°C for 24h. The dried banana fiber was cut to small pieces and sieved to obtain the uniform size. The banana fiber was kept in dry in a glass container for further usage.

B. Treatment of Banana Stems Fiber

Chemical treatments were used for the modification of adsorbent by using NaOH and KOH. The dried banana fiber (17.21g) was soaked with 1.0M NaOH for 3h at room temperature. The NaOH-treated banana fiber was rinsed with deionized water until the washing was free from color, this is to ensure there is no excess NAOH solution from the soaking process present. The banana fiber was dried again in the oven for 115° C and was labelled as NaOH-banana fiber (NBF). For chemical modification using KOH, the same procedure was used where the modified banana fiber now is known as KOH-banana fiber (KBF). The chemically treated banana fiber was kept inside a glass bottle for further usage.

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C. Preparation of Oil Contaminated Water Sample

The adsorption study was conducted using raw and both chemically treated banana fiber adsorbent on oil contaminated water at room temperature. The adsorbent oil mixture was stirred for 30 min on an orbital shaker at 170 rpm. The mixture was then being filtered and the filtrate was then analyzed for oil content. Determination of oil content in water was conducted by using USEPA solid phase extraction method 10300. the percentage of oil removal was determined from the equation below:

$$\text{Percentage of removal (\%)} = \frac{C_o - C_e}{C_o}$$

Where, C_o is the initial concentration (mg/l) in diesel oil contaminated water and C_e are the concentration (mg/l) of oil after the adsorption process occurs.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 below shows the oil adsorptivity test result from the three different types of the sorbent. It shows that the concentration of the filtered oil contaminated water decreased from 0.28 mg/l to 0.19 mg/l in sample S1, 0.11 mg/L in sample S2 and 0.04 in sample S3. The percentage of removals is 32.14%, 60.71% and 85.71% for sorbent sample S1, S2 and S3 respectively. It shows that the treatment of the banana fiber using alkaline solution was able to improve the sorbent capacity of the banana fiber. The chemical treatment used has modified the banana stem fiber surface which improves the characteristics of the fiber as oil removal.

TABLE 1 : Result of The Use of Oil And Grease Test

Descriptions	The concentration of Oil in oil contaminated water Before filtration			The concentration of Oil in oil contaminated water After Filtration		
	Untreated	NaOH	KOH	Untreated (S1)	NaOH (S2)	KOH (S3)
Concentration of oil (mg/l)	0.28	0.28	0.28	0.19	0.11	0.04
Percentage concentration of oil (%)	100	100	100	67.27	40.13	98.23
Percentage of oil removal (%)	-	-	-	32.14	60.71	85.71

The decreasing amounts of the concentration indicate that the banana stem fibers are one of the good sorption materials and treatment can further improve its sorbent ability. This result is supported by the research that was done by Mohapatra, Mishra and Sutar (2010), where the banana fiber being as natural sorbent has a high ability to absorb the spilled oils in refineries.

In comparison to the treated fiber, the concentration of the oil in the water sample decreasing from 0.28 mg/l to 0.11 mg/l of using the treated Sodium Hydroxide (NaOH) banana stem fiber and 0.04 mg/l after using the treated Potassium Hydroxide (KOH) banana stem fiber. From the results, it shows the higher removal by treated fiber compared with untreated raw fiber. The entrapment of oil at the surface of adsorbent is believed due to the removal of the outer coating of the fiber (Wahi *et al.*, 2013).

CONCLUSION

From the result, we can conclude that the treated sorbent shows a higher removal when compared with the untreated sorbent. This is due to the removal of wax in the outer layer of the sorbent. Since the decreasing amount of concentration of oil shows that chemical treatment may catalyst the sorption of oil from the water. Thus, the uses of the alkaline solution in modifying the surface structure of the banana stem fiber can cause the banana stem fiber to work efficiently in removing the oil from the water sample. Therefore, this paper highlights a new method which has been conducted to help in oil spill removal technology and the effect from the uses of the different chemical in treating the fiber.

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REFERENCES

- i. *Abdullah, M. A., Rahmah, A. U. & Man, Z. (2010). Physicochemical And Sorption Characteristics Of Malaysian Ceiba Pentandra (L.) Gaertn. As A Natural Oil Sorbent. J Hazard Mater 177(1-3), 683-691.*
- ii. *Al-Majed, A. A., Adebayo, A. R. & Hossain, M. E. (2012). A Novel Sustainable Oil Spill Control Technology. Environmental Engineering and Management Journal, 333-353.*
- iii. *Hubbe, M. A., Rojas, O. J., Fingas, M. & Gupta, B. S. Cellulosic Substrates For Removal Of Pollutants From Aqueous Systems: A Review. Spilled oil and emulsified organic liquids. BioResources, 8(2), 3038-3097.*
- iv. *Mohapatra, D., Mishra, S., & Sutar, N. (2010). Banana And Its By-Product Utilization: An Overview. J Sci Ind Res, 69(5), 323-329.*
- v. *Sakari, M., Zakaria, M. P., Mohamed, C. A. R., Lajis, N. H., Chandru, K., Bahry, P. S. & Anita, S. (2010). The History Of Petroleum Pollution In Malaysia: Urgent Need For Integrated Prevention Approach. Environ Asia, 3, 131-142.*
- vi. *Sarbatly, R., Krishnaiah, D. & Kamin, Z. (2016). A Review Of Polymer Nanofibres By Electrospinning And Their Application In Oil-Water Separation For Cleaning Up Marine Oil Spills. Marine pollution bulletin, 106(1), 8-16.*
- vii. *Sidik, S. M., Jalil, A. A., Triwahyono, S., Adam, S. H., Satar, M. A. H. & Hameed, V. (2012). Modified Oil Palm Leaves Adsorbent With Enhanced Hydrophobicity For Crude Oil Removal. Chemical Engineering Journal, 203, 9-18. doi: 10.1016/j.cej.2012.06.132.*
- viii. *Sun, X. F., Sun, R. C., & Sun, J. X. (2004). Acetylation Of Sugarcane Bagasse Using NBS As A Catalyst Under Mild Reaction Conditions For The Production Of Oil Sorption-Active Materials. Bioresour Technol, 95(3), 343-350. doi: 10.1016/j.biortech.2004.02.025.*
- ix. *Teli M. D. & Valia, S. P. (2012). Acetylation Of Banana Fibre To Improve Oil Absorbency. Carbohydr Polym, 92(1), 328-333. doi: 10.1016/j.carbpol.2012.09.019.*
- x. *Wahi, R., Chuah, L. A., Choong, T. S. Y., Ngaini, Z., & Nourouzi, V. (2013). Oil Removal From Aqueous State By Natural Fibrous Sorbent: An Overview. Separation and Purification Technology, 113, 51-63. doi: 10.1016/j.seppur.2013.04.015.*